

VEGETATION DYNAMICS IN COMMUNITY RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AREAS: A MEASURE OF PROGRESS

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Abstract

*Ghana's Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs) are established to reduce biodiversity degradation through the promotion of communal responsibility to conserve resources for sustainable benefits. This study was conducted to assess vegetation dynamics in three CREMAs in the northern savanna zone of Ghana through the application of remote sensing techniques and field observation. The findings showed the vegetation cover of all the three study areas improved over the period between 1990 and 2010. There were indications of successions from lower tier vegetation classes to higher ones. The riparian vegetation of the study sites changed from open savanna woodland to closed savanna woodland mainly through the grazing activities of the hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibious*) and management practices that restrict farming, livestock grazing, charcoal production and suppress wildfires. The suppression of wildfires has resulted in considerable amount of fuel load which must be managed to prevent severe-intensive-fires in the future. Notwithstanding the general improvement in vegetation cover, there were also considerable increased coverage of bare surface/built up areas indicating economic activities also moved up over the period.*

Key words: biodiversity, community, ecotourism, savanna, vegetation, wildfire

INTRODUCTION

Ghana's Ministry of Environment Science and Technology (MEST) in 2012 identified northern Ghana to have had prolonged history of land degradation which has resulted in desertification at certain parts of the northern zone of the country. Again, a report on Ghana from the country's Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources (MLNR) in 2012 stated 135,000 ha of forest cover is lost annually through: (1) expansive agriculture, (2) increasing urbanization, (3) mining and mineral extraction and (4) harvesting of wood for lumber and fuel. The alarming degradation of the country's land resources has resulted in the formulation of new strategies aim to halt biodiversity losses and promote sustainable development (Wood, 2008).

The Government of Ghana and development partners engage communities to work towards stopping the degradation through different sets of interventions. One of the strategies being implemented to halt the continuous land degradation is through promoting the establishment of Community Resources Management Areas (CREMAs). As at the year 2009 the total area covered by CREMAs in Ghana was 200,000 ha (Roe et al., 2009). Again, by the year 2010, there were 26 active CREMAs that had

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been established in Ghana (Asare et al., 2013). The Wildlife Division of Ghana devolve authority to managing biodiversity to local institutions that set up CREMAs.

The CREMA strategy intervention aim is not only to stop biodiversity degradation, but also to help regeneration of the ecosystem to its optimum productive levels that will support rural livelihoods (Ekpe et al., 2014; Owusu-Ansah, 2019). The establishment of CREMAs is to promote sustainable utilization of biodiversity resources through good governance structures that are locally developed. The CREMA structures consist of regulations and alternative livelihood support programmes that are implemented through collaboration with other institutions at the local level to manage biodiversity resources (Owusu-Ansah, 2019). Community leaders who lead the process are expected to enforce conservation laws which include antipoaching patrols, prevent wildfires and other forms of encroachment that degrade biodiversity resources.

This study assessed the vegetation dynamics of three Community Resources Management Areas (CREMAs) that have been established in the fragile ecosystem of northern Ghana. The sites are Wechiau Community Hippopotamus Sanctuary (WCHS), Zukpri Integrated Wildlife Sanctuary (ZIWS) and Sayinga-Kasena-Gavara-Kara (SKGK). These sites are prone to annual wildfires and other human induced degradation such as illegal felling of trees for lumber and charcoal production. Overgrazing by livestock (especially from nomadic herdsman cattle) is also more pronounced in the northern savanna zone. Biodiversity and other forms of land degradation are exacerbated by an annual short duration rainfall and high temperatures which make this zone of Ghana vulnerable to wildfires (MLNR, 2012).

The study purpose was to track changes in the vegetation cover of the three sites between 1990 and 2010. Huge amounts of biodiversity resources are devolved to community leaders to manage when CREMAs are established (Roe et al., 2009). Failure to properly manage these resources by the community leaders will lead to further degradation. The resources then will be regarded as open access leading to abuse in the manner of the 'tragedy of the commons' (Moxnes, 1998). If that was to happen, it would be improper and a disincentive to the Government to continue to implement the CREMA strategies. Changes in the vegetation cover of the study sites were used to gauge progress in biodiversity management effectiveness in the CREMAs to prevent degradation (Leeuwen et al., 2010).

Theoretical Background

The ineffectiveness of centralized government biodiversity conservation programmes has been debated in the literature. Biodiversity resources degradation causes have sometimes been blamed on centralized management concepts (Agrawal and Gibson, 1999; Lockwood et al., 2010).

Indeed, one major reason to the disregard for conservation laws in communities are placed on the enmity that results from centralization policies such as the creation of protected areas to the exclusion of rural people (Agyare, 2013; Bixler et al., 2015; Grodzinska-Jurczak et al., 2012). CREMAs in Ghana are set up to reduce some of the negative impacts of centralized conservation strategies through collaboration between government and communal structures established to manage biodiversity.

The CREMA strategy guidelines have been targeted at putting more lands under conservation. The problem with this strategy however, is that the Ghana Government does not own large tracts of lands for conservation because most land tenure arrangements in the country are under traditional rulers and families (Agyare, 2013; Roe et al., 2009). The approach to circumvent this difficulty is to promote the implementation of collaborative biodiversity resources conservation policies in the country (The Wildlife Division, 2000).

The argument for the implementation of collaborative conservation strategies is to get some communal lands to be put under conservation without the enmity that characterizes centralized protected area regimes (Jones and Erdmann, 2013; Kluvánková-Oravská et al., 2009; Shafer, 2015). The strategy does not only promote participatory conservation services in rural areas, it is also a means of promoting alternative livelihoods programmes to improve standard of living (Ekpe et al., 2014). The CREMA strategy implementation focus has been on areas with rich biodiversity which has greater risk to degradation. Monitoring progress to see the established CREMAs do not suffer degradation is not only to perpetuate the resources, but also to replicate the programme and its benefits in other areas.

Liu et al., 2016 emphasized the need to monitor vegetation dynamics especially in ecosystems like the savanna where negative human activities combine with harsh abiotic conditions to degrade biodiversity resources. Remote sensing techniques have been useful in monitoring changes in vegetations at a large scale. Different vegetation types and characteristics respond variably to remote sensing application. It has been stated that moisture content, chlorophyll and other pigment levels in plants have varied sensitive levels and respond differently to remote sensing techniques. The technology is used to differentiate among vegetation types (Leeuwen et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2016; Norman et al., 2014).

The main objective of this research was to understand how the CREMA leaders have been able to prevent the degradation of the biodiversity resources that has been entrusted unto them. Vegetation trend analysis has been used in determining management activities effectiveness (Norman et al., 2014). The assumption to this study was that effective management of the CREMAs prevent vegetation degradation which leads to

lower level vegetation classes succeeding to higher ones. The trend analysis of this study considered the changes in the percentage coverage of the different vegetation classes at three temporal points.

Two research questions were asked for the study.

(1). What are the trends in vegetation cover since the conservation sensitization/ education and enforcement activities began in the CREMAs?

(2). How would the changes in the different vegetation classes impact on: (I) wildfire management, (II) herbivory and (III) ecotourism development in the CREMAs?

This study was used to triangulate with interview and field observation data collected for the author's doctoral dissertation. It was to attest to the responses of the CREMA leaders that suggest they had been able to reduce the incidences of wildfires, poaching, overgrazing and farming close to riparian areas in the CREMAs.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study Sites

Three CREMAs were purposively selected for this study (Devers and Frankel, 2000) because they occur in the same ecological zone. Sayinga-Kasena-Gavara-Kara (SKGK), Wechiau Community Hippopotamus Sanctuary (WCHS) and Zukpri Integrated Wildlife Sanctuary (ZIWS) are located in the Guinea savanna ecological zone. The SKGK is located between latitudes 10°45' 45''N and 11°00' 12'' N and longitudes 1°18' 00'' W and 1° 39' 00'' W with a total area of 587.26 km² (The Wildlife Division, 2017). The total land area of ZIWS is 420 km². ZIWS is located within latitude 10° 00' 00'' N and 10° 20'00'' N and longitude 2° 30'00'' W and 2° 50' 00'' W in the Upper West Region of Ghana. WCHS can be found in the Wa West District of the Upper West Region lying between latitudes 9° 40' 05'' N and 10° 10' 47''N and also between longitudes 2° 20' 00''W and 2° 50' 30''W (Ghana Statistical Service, 2010). Both WCHS and ZIWS lie in the same continuum of land mass drained by the Black Volta and its tributaries.

The three CREMAs are populated by different types of wildlife species that enrich the biodiversity of the ecosystem. For example, WCHS and ZIWS have sizeable populations of hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibious*) which inhabit the Black Volta (Olayide et al., 2013). Primates species like the Patas Monkey (*Erythrocebus patas*), and the Baboon (*Papio anubis*) are also common in the study sites. The SKGK also has a sizeable population of roan antelope (*Hippotragus equines*) and the place is particularly known to be part of the annual migration route of Elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) from Burkina Faso to Ghana (Lungren, 2008). Large number of cattle herds (particularly from nomads) traverse the study sites.

Methods

A time series vegetation map was developed for each of the selected sites over three temporal points (the years 1990, 2000 and 2010) to relate vegetation cover changes. Field visits were undertaken to each of the study sites and locations with closed canopy tall trees were selected. Estimated centers of such closed savanna woodlands in each of the study sites were marked with Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates. A time series vegetation maps were developed from the coordinate points through remote sensing techniques (Maurin et al., 2015) to study the changes in the vegetation cover over a twenty - year period (1990 to 2010). In all nine images were developed for analysis.

The images developed were for dry season (late March) at each time point to eliminate possible influences of annual crop fields on the vegetation percentage coverage. The timing for the images was to get the optimum natural vegetation coverage for analysis devoid of crop fields. Also, the effects of wildfires would have been felt by late March when the images were developed (Norman, 2014). The time series imagery maps of the CREMAs were developed for 1990 which predates their establishments. Images were developed for 2000 which marked the CREMAs formative stages and 2010 which gave ample time to assess the effectiveness in halting degradation of the vegetation (Leeuwen et al., 2010).

Data Analyses

Savanna vegetation has many succession classes (Maurin et al., 2015). In this study, the savanna vegetation has been classified to include in a descending order closed savanna woodland, followed by open savanna woodland, which is also followed by dense herbaceous /grass vegetation. The rest of the classes are grass herbaceous vegetation and bare surface/built up areas. The Black Volta River coverage area was also determined for WCHS and ZIWS.

The percentage coverage of each vegetation class at each temporal point were related in the analyses to observe the trends in the changes. Findings have been presented in descriptive tables showing areas covered in square kilometers and percentage coverage of each vegetation class.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The series for this section begins with WCHS, followed by ZIWS and then SKGK. The discussions section brings into perspectives the observed changes in vegetation cover, focusing on its implication on: (1) wildfire management, (2) herbivory and (3) promoting ecotourism.

Vegetation Cover Changes in WCHS

The analyses were based on a sampled area of 33.99 Km² of WCHS as seen in Fig. 1. The general observation was that there had been

improvement in the vegetation cover. There was a general trend of the lower-class vegetation types succeeding into higher levels. Details in the changes in the vegetation types in WCHS is shown below (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Time Series Image Map of WCHS for 1990, 2000 and 2010

Table 1

Matrix of land cover by class for the years 1990, 2000 and 2010 in WCHS

Vegetation Class	Year of Assessment					
	1990		2000		2010	
	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover
Closed savanna woodland	0.5587	1.64	2.8287	8.32	2.8301	8.32
Open savanna woodland	9.840	28.95	8.9712	26.39	9.6062	28.26
Dense herbaceous/grass cover	17.1903	50.57	14.9032	43.84	16.5132	48.58
Grass/herbaceous cover	6.0354	17.75	5.36402	15.78	2.3256	6.84
Bare surface/built up areas	0.270	0.79	0.8226	2.42	2.1348	6.28
Water body	0.0972	0.28	1.1034	3.25	0.5832	1.72
Total	33.9931	100	33.9931	100	33.9931	100

WCHS in the year 1990 had the largest portion of its vegetation as dense herbaceous/grass made up of 50.57 % which reduced considerably to 43.84 % by the year 2000. However, there was a major increase of this vegetation class from the 43.84 % in 2000 to 48.57 % in 2010. The inching up of the percentage coverage of the dense herbaceous/grass vegetation could only be attributed to a higher succession from the lower grass herbaceous, class which percentage coverage reduced over the same period (2000 to 2010) from 15.77 % to 6.84 %.

The closed savanna woodland forms the highest class of the vegetation succession ladder in the West African savanna ecosystem. This vegetation class in 1990 covered only 1.64 %. The closed savanna woodland vegetation moved up to 8.31 % by the year 2000. As it is expected, its lower tier-the open savanna vegetation class had its coverage reduced a little from 28.94 % to 26.39 %. This suggests a succession to the upper class of the closed savanna woodland occurred from the second tier. The closed savanna vegetation maintained its coverage with the same percentage of 8.32 % in 2010 as it was in 2000.

The Black Volta is an important international water body for Ghana and Burkina Faso. The River covered 0.28 % of the sampled area as at 1990. The Black Volta coverage increased to 1.10 % in 2000. However, the River in 2010 reduced to almost half of its 2000 figure. In 2000, the River occupied 1.10 Km² as against the 0.58 Km² in 2010. Seasonal changes in climatic conditions would have been the major cause of the variations.

Bare surface/built areas in WCHS were relatively small covering 0.79 % in 1990. It increased to 2.42 % over the ten-year period between 1990 and 2000. The bare surface/built up areas continued to increase and within the period between 2000 and 2010, it jumped from 2.41 % to 6.84 %. The movement upwards of this vegetation class suggest an increase in human settlements and activities that degrade the vegetation occurred.

Vegetation Cover Changes in ZIWS

The analyses were based on a sampled area of 43.22 Km² of the ZIWS. ZIWS lies at the north of WCHS on the course of the Black Volta River. The general observation was that there was an improvement in the vegetation cover, notwithstanding a considerable increase in the bare surface/built up areas over the twenty-year period. There were general trends of lower tier vegetation classes succeeding into higher levels (Fig. 2). The percentage changes in the vegetation cover that occurred over the period is shown below (Table 2).

In 1990, more than half of the ZIWS' sampled area was made up of a dense herbaceous/grass of 55.73 % which was followed by open savanna woodland covering 29.68 %. The dense herbaceous/grass vegetation reduced by a little over eight percentage points to 47.95 % in 2000.

However, there was no major change in the dense herbaceous/grass vegetation percentage coverage by 2010. It only dropped by 0.89 % of what was recorded in 2000. This change is in contrast to the major increase that was observed in the same class of vegetation in WCHS from 43.84 % to 48.57 % between 2000 and 2010.

Fig. 2. Time Series Map of ZIWS for 1990, 2000 and 2010

Table 2

Matrix of land cover by class for the years 1990, 2000 and 2010 in ZIWS

Vegetation Class	Year of Assessment					
	1990		2000		2010	
	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover
Closed savanna woodland	0.8343	1.93	1.0998	2.55	1.152	2.67
Open savanna woodland	12.8287	29.68	14.0122	32.42	10.854	25.11
Dense herbaceous/grass cover	24.0868	55.73	20.7253	47.95	20.3393	47.06
Grass/herbaceous cover	3.7539	8.69	3.501	8.1	6.642	15.37
Bare surface/built up areas	1.1196	2.59	2.9601	6.85	3.9204	9.07
Water body	0.594	1.38	0.9189	2.13	0.3096	0.72
Total	43.217	100	43.2173	100	43.2173	100

The closed savanna woodland (the highest vegetation class) stood at 1.93 % which was slightly higher than the 1.64 % recorded for WCHS in 1990. The closed savanna woodland vegetation did not increase substantially compared to what was observed in WCHS where it moved from 1.64 % to 8.31 % between 1990 and 2000. In ZIWS, it increased marginally from 1.93 % to 2.55 %. Again, it increased marginally from 2.55 % to 2.67 % between 2000 and 2010.

The Black Volta River covered 1.38 % compared to the 0.28 % of WCHS in 1990. The River's percentage coverage increased from 1.38 % in 1990 to 2.13 % in 2000. Again, the seasonal variation in climatic conditions would be the major cause of the differences in the Black Volta coverage as was also observed for WCHS over the same period. The River in 2010 saw a reduction in its coverage to 0.72 % in 2010. Again, the drop in the volume of the water suggest harsher climatic conditions variation over the period might have occurred.

The bare surface /built areas for ZIWS in 1990 was 2.59 % which was higher than the 0.79 % recorded for WCHS. The bare surface/built up areas increased to 6.85 % in 2000. This was a marked difference from the changes that occurred in WCHS, which increased from 0.79 % to 2.42 %. By 2010, the bare surface/built up areas in ZIWS had increased from 6.85 % to 9.07 %. The 9.07 % was the highest conversion of vegetation cover into a bare surface/built up area of the three study sites. Expansion in human activities including settlements and economic activities were the major causes for the conversion into bare surface/built areas.

Vegetation Cover Changes in SKGK

The analyses were based on a sampled area of 71.5 Km² of the SKGK. River Sissili and its tributaries are the main drainage of the CREMA. This River completely dries up in the dry season and therefore its percentage coverage was not shown in the images for analysis. There are substantial sections along this River that have riparian forests. The riparian forest serves as an important wildlife corridor between protected areas in Burkina Faso and Ghana. Fig. 3 shows the changes in vegetation coverage that occurred in the SKGK. Details of the changes that occurred over the period is shown below (Table 3).

The SKGK in the year 1990 had the largest vegetation class as dense herbaceous/grass covering 46.86%. This class was followed by open savanna woodland making 33.08% of the sampled area. The dense herbaceous/grass vegetation reduced from 46.82% to 41.03% by the year 2000 and it reduced further to 37.57% in 2010. The reductions suggest a succession to the upper open savanna vegetation woodland occurred. This

was confirmed by the open savanna vegetation steadily increment in coverage between 2000 and 2010.

Fig. 3. Time Series Image Map of SKGK for 1990, 2000 and 2010

Table 3

Matrix of land cover by class for the years 1990, 2000 and 2010 in SKGK

Vegetation Class	Year of Assessment					
	1990		2000		2010	
	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover
Closed savanna woodland	3.0663	4.29	3.8691	5.41	5.5444	7.75
Open savanna woodland	23.6503	33.08	23.5392	32.92	28.1672	39.39
Dense herbaceous/grass cover	33.4792	46.82	29.3428	41.03	26.8668	37.57
Grass/herbaceous cover	10.4148	14.57	14.1098	19.73	8.5292	11.93
Bare surface/built up areas	0.8901	1.24	0.6489	0.91	2.3996	3.36
Total	71.5010	100	71.5098	100	71.5072	100

The open savanna woodland moved from 32.92 % to 39.39 % over the period. The changes in the open savanna woodland would not have been contributed by the dense herbaceous alone looking at the margin of increase. The grass herbaceous class also reduced from 19.73 % to 11.93 % between

2000 and 2010. This suggests a succession from this class to two tier classes above occurred.

The closed savanna woodland which form the highest class of the vegetation succession ladder covered 4.29 % in 1990. This percentage coverage happened to be the highest within this class of vegetation among the three study sites in 1990. By the year 2000 the closed savanna woodland vegetation moved up to 5.41 % and further moved to 7.75 % in 2010. The open savanna woodland vegetation reduced marginally from 33.08 % to 32.92 % between 1990 and 2000. This suggests a succession to the upper closed savanna woodland occurred. This is confirmed by the marginal increase of the closed savanna woodland from 4.29 % to 5.41 % over the period.

The bare surface/built areas coverage was 1.24 % in 1990 which surprisingly reduced to 0.91 % by 2000. That was the only situation where a reduction occurred in this class of vegetation within a ten-year period in any of the study sites. However, between 2000 and 2010 there was an increase from 0.91 % to 3.36 %. The increment was largely contributed by the level of human settlement developments that moved up over the period. A cursory look at the satellite image showed communities which were essentially dots expanded considerably over the period (Fig. 3).

Improved Vegetation Cover: Implications for Wildfire Management

The threat of wildfires and its intensity increase with drier conditions coupled with higher fuel load that result from previous unburnt vegetation (Sebata, 2017). Findings from Gordijn et al., 2012, cited in Sebata, 2017 indicated that when areas are suppressed from the effect of wildfires for long, it results in woody plant vegetation. On the contrary incidences of wildfires reduce the number of adult trees in the savanna by killing seedlings and saplings (Campbell, 2013). At seedling and sapling stages of tree development, it is unable to resist and recover from some of the intense fires of the savanna. Wildfires however, has the advantage to reduce competition thereby increasing growth rate of few trees that survive.

Savanna vegetation has been predicted to undergo major changes in ecological functions and processes (Baudena et al., 2015; IPCC, 2007). The prediction was based on the effects of global warming which affect moisture content of plants and grasses in the savanna. The consequence of that prediction was a heightened incidences of annual wildfire regimes in the savanna. The ultimate outcome will be losses in biodiversity in the savanna ecosystem due to fragmentation (Liu et al., 2016). However, the general trend in the vegetation dynamics in the three CREMAs suggested the vegetation has been managed well with lower tier classes succeeding to higher ones. The findings from the satellite imagery and field observations

pointed the leaders have been able to reduce some of the threats such as wildfires and indiscriminate felling of trees within as well as regulating farming activities in sensitive ecological zones.

Notwithstanding the findings of an improved vegetation cover in the CREMAs, the predictions of Baudena et al. (2015) and the IPCC (2007) still looms particularly in the drier areas of the CREMAs. The sampled areas for this study were mostly the riparian forests where closed canopy vegetation existed and incidentally these areas were designated in the CREMAs as core zones where little human activities were allowed. The moisture content of the riparian vegetation is relatively higher compared to vegetation types further from the waterbodies. The riparian vegetation does not suffer much losses to wildfires and other threats that negatively impact on the vegetation (Norman et al., 2014). These factors would have accounted for the observed improved vegetation cover of the CREMAs.

However, there are considerable fuel loads that have built up at the unburnt areas of the CREMAs and any spark of wildfires could be devastating (Sebata, 2017). Efforts like conservation education, creating fire belts and enforcing regulations should be constant in the CREMAs, so as to prevent fires that could severely impact on biodiversity. Controlled burning regimes have to be promoted, to reduce fuel loads to prevent devastating wildfire episodes from occurring (Goodenough et al., 2016).

Improved Vegetation Cover: Implications for Herbivory

Herbivory, either by grazers or browsers together with wildfires is considered to be one of the major factors that disturbs savanna ecosystems (Liu et al., 2016; Sebata, 2017). Herbivory alone has considerable impacts on the vegetation cover classes of the savanna. Chritz et al., 2016 stated megaherbivores like the hippopotamus and elephants have the capacity to change the savanna ecosystem by their herbivory. Hippopotamus feeding intensity on grass vegetation reduces them into swards that are found on the banks of their aquatic habitat (Kanga et al., 2011). Habitat dominated by hippopotamus promote woody vegetation stands along waterbodies through their feeding habits (Chritz et al., 2016; Kanga et al., 2011).

This study findings showed an increasing closed savanna woodland vegetation along the Black Volta River in WCHS and ZIWS. For example, WCHS closed Savanna woodland vegetation percentage coverage increased from 1.64 % to 8.31 % between 1990 and 2010. This finding suggests the effort to conserve the hippopotamus yielded, the benefit of increasing woodland coverage. A combination of management practices and the feeding habits of the hippopotamus resulted in a succession of lower tier vegetation classes to higher ones.

The leaders of the CREMAs have to continue controlling livestock grazing in the core zones to limit competition between cattle and

hippopotamus (Kanga et al., 2011). An increasing number of hippopotamus will benefit the CREMA as it has the potential to increase the number of tourist visits to the CREMAs.

Improved Vegetation Cover and Ecotourism Development

Ecotourism development is one of the main objectives that drive the establishment of CREMAs. The purpose is to create alternative livelihoods that will ease the pressure on the extraction of biodiversity for subsistence (Ekpe et al., 2014). The dynamics between grassland and woody vegetation in the savanna oscillate in an equilibrium among variations in the levels of wildfires, moisture, soil stability and herbivory (Sebata, 2017).

According to Arbieu et al., 2017, open savanna vegetation is essential to the development of wildlife base ecotourism. The essence is that the open savanna increases visibility for tourists to appreciate wildlife. Dynamics in savanna vegetation also alter habitat, home ranges and feeding regimes of wildlife. Arbieu et al., 2017 again, reported dense vegetation cover reduced tourists viewing satisfaction perception of wildlife species.

The findings of this study showed there had been shifts in succession from lower tier vegetation classes to the highest-closed savanna woodland vegetation. However, this class of vegetation still covers relatively a smaller area in all the three CREMAs which would not pose challenge for tourists viewing. The two largest vegetation classes in all the CREMAs were the open savanna woodland and the dense herbaceous/grass vegetation.

Generally, there were successions from the lower dense herbaceous/grass vegetation to the higher open savanna woodland in all the three CREMAs for the period. These two sets of vegetation classes are essential to promote wildlife tourism. They increase visibility compared to the closed savanna woodland (Arbieu et al., 2017) and also, promote herbivory by ungulates (Chritz et al., 2016; Kanga et al., 2011; Sebata, 2017).

The CREMA management should take note about these two sets of vegetation in developing their tourism products to generate revenue to run their activities, and also, to provide alternative livelihoods for the communities.

Management should not only be obsessed in preventing wildfires to promote successions to closed savanna woodlands, but have an integrated approach that will promote grazing and controlled burning regimes to keep an open savanna woodland and dense herbaceous/grass vegetation (Sebata, 2017). Such management activities will be beneficial in generating fresh growth for herbivory (Kanga et al., 2011) for a productive savanna ecosystem (Chritz et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2016).

CONCLUSIONS

Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs) are established to reduce biodiversity degradation through the promotion of communal responsibility to conserve the resources for sustainable benefits. This study assessed vegetation dynamics in three CREMAs in Ghana. The purpose was to determine management effectiveness outcomes in reducing biodiversity degradation by assessing changes in the vegetation cover. Satellite images and field observations were used to track changes in the vegetation cover of the CREMAs.

The findings showed the vegetation cover of all the three study areas improved over the period between 1990 and 2010. There were successions from lower tier vegetation classes to higher ones. The leaders of the CREMAs have controlled threats like wildfires, overgrazing and tree felling for lumber and charcoal production. The CREMAs conservation activities have been conservation education, law enforcement, creation of wildfire belts and promotion of alternative livelihood programmes to improve biodiversity sustainability.

The benefits of implementing these activities were seen in an increasing coverage of closed savanna woodland vegetation in the CREMAs. The established closed savanna woodland vegetation along the banks of the Black Volta were the results of the hippopotamus grazing activities coupled with conservation activities in WCHS and ZIWS.

The management of the CREMAs have been able to suppress incidences of wildfires in the core zones, which has resulted in fuel load accumulation. Constant measures have to be put in place to prevent any spark of fires because it could be devastating due to the high intensity of such fires. The conservation activities have benefited the ungulates and other wildlife populations in the CREMAs.

The CREMAs objective of promoting wildlife tourism could be enhanced with increasing biodiversity and abundance. Tourists satisfaction dips with closed woody vegetation. The CREMA management should promote and maintain open savanna and dense herbaceous/grass vegetation for viewing satisfaction and grazing opportunities for tourists and wildlife respectively.

The major challenge to the vegetation cover of the CREMAs was the increasing percentage coverage of the bare surface/built up areas which increased from 0.79 % to 6.84 % in WCHS over the period. Similar trends were observed for ZIWS and SKGK for the period between 1990 and 2010. For ZIWS the bare surface/built up areas increased from 2.59 % to 9.07 % and for SKGK it moved up from 1.24 % to 3.36 %.

The change in ZIWS bare surface/built areas was the highest percentage change among the three CREMAs. The increasing human settlements and its economic activities particularly those related to agriculture, charcoal burning and logging of trees pose major threats to the vegetation cover of the CREMAs.

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